

Intention to migrate among young adults

We assess the percentage of young people intending to move to another country within the next 3 years using the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) data collected from 2020-2024.

Respondents were asked if they **intend to move to another country within the next 3 years.**

The percentage of people definitely or probably intending to move abroad ranges from under 3% in Czechia to over 28% in Moldova, indicating **large cross-country differences** in emigration plans.

In Moldova, 32.5% of men plan to move abroad, exceeding women's 23.5%. Denmark also shows a gap favouring men (12.4% vs. 8.2%), and **men likewise report higher intentions** in Norway and the UK. In contrast, Czechia (1.7% vs. 4.1%) and Sweden (6.3% vs. 9.7%) both exhibit higher rates for women, while Austria and Finland show a small difference, but still **higher intentions among women.**

INTENTION TO MOVE TO ANOTHER COUNTRY WITHIN THE NEXT 3 YEARS

GGs DATA OFFERS VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO VARIOUS FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH EMIGRATION INTENTIONS.

Source: Generations and Gender Survey Round II – wave 1 (data from 2020-2024)

The Generations and Gender Programme Preparatory Phase Project (GGP-5D)